

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON TEACHING LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has created a global plight that has a great impact on how we perceive our world and our routine lives. The pandemic has ignited a conversation and a global realisation by breaking our perception of what is normal and has deconstructed our society as we know it. Various countries around the world, including the most developed nations are facing a complete slowdown in all sectors. One of the critical sectors, which are facing a complete downturn, is the education sector. In light of the global crisis, the governments of countries across the globe have implemented the closure of educational institutions in order to contain the transmission of the deadly virus. The closure of educational institutes has not only affected the lives of students but also of teachers and parents. But, as a messiah comes the concept of Digital Learning, bringing educational institutions to students, when they have to stay indoors. Digital teaching is the delivery of learning, training or education programs by electronic means. The growing use of Digital Learning has led to a paradigm shift in the attitude of the people towards the same. But, Technology comes with its own advantages and disadvantages. This research paper gauges the positive and negative impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on the education sector which includes the students and the teachers.

Key words: Covid-19, Digital Learning, Education Sector

1.1 Introduction

“Education is a gift which no one can take away.” Not even a virus!

Education unlocks the mind and expands our horizon. It is like stepping out of the darkness into the light. The Covid-19 pandemic has paralysed the education sector. Most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions to contain the spread of the disease. According to UNESCO, Nationwide closure in 156 countries affects about 1.21 billion students amounting 70% of the student population across the globe. The make-up of schooling and learning were the first to be disrupted by the closure of schools and other institutions. Students have been unable to continue their learning process and the teachers have been unable to finish the assessment process due to the lockdown imposed by countries worldwide. But there is a ray of hope as most of the institutions have started their classes online. As traditional methods of teaching cannot be put to use during this crippling crisis, the teaching faculty had to come up with new means and methods to carry out the learning and assessment process by having a tighter relationship with technology.

In a country like India, where a nationwide lockdown was introduced overnight, educational institutes had to switch over from their age-old ways of teaching to online learning within a short time span. The Indian Education System has seen a paradigm shift from classroom to Digital Learning. The pandemic has been seen as a harbinger of a shift from conventional gathering to online meetings. During this time of quarantine, various e-learning platforms have come

forward and have offered students, a comprehensive array of courses in different fields by various prestigious institutions worldwide. Now Students can access these courses and continue the learning process from home.

Online Classes - a growing trend

With social distancing measures in place, students and teachers cannot physically gather together. Thus, online lecture has emerged as a key to continue learning.

“Remember that schools are not closed. School buildings are closed. The teachers and staff are working harder than ever”

Schools and Colleges across India have been forced to shift to Online Classes overnight. Though this had led to a lot of confusion initially, once the starting troubles passed, things have gotten back as close to normalcy as possible. Students and Teachers are now comfortable and well acquainted with the softwares used and have gotten used to learning from home.

Necessity is truly the Mother of Invention, as teachers have found innovative ways to engage students with learning by using audiovisual media, presentations and taking quizzes through the School/College Moodle or Google Forms. Many teachers have in fact begun recording their lectures to put on the School/College Moodles or even on YouTube for students to go back and refer later.

It is also interesting to see how Educational Institutions have been using Online Video Conferencing to beat the Lockdown Blues. Many schools and colleges have organised Yoga sessions, GK Quizzes, MUN (Model United Nations) Conferences and Webinars through video conferencing apps, to help students keep themselves busy, fit and learning. In fact, even Hobby classes have decided to not let the pandemic come in between kids and their talents and have continued their classes by using online video conferencing.

Growth of Online Courses & Industrial Training

Covid-19 has greatly impacted the industrial sectors leading to a lot of changes. People are working from home with the help of technology. Here, Technology has assumed a growingly important role, which is sure to continue post the lockdown.

Learning from home does not just pertain to university education. Many companies offer their employees access to many courses and webinars, which is also included in learning. Conducting seminars is a way of training and educating employees to the latest information. Since gatherings are prohibited now, webinars are being conducted online.

There are various Online Courses offered by various renowned universities to utilize this free time effectively. For example, Harvard offers various certificate courses for students and professionals to develop skills. The relevance of this example is that in the future, such courses can create time and cost utility as you can learn from reputed Foreign institutions sitting at home. TCS ION has also come up with a Soft-Skills Development course for students to utilise their time effectively. Thus, learning has not stopped, rather become much more flexible

1.2 SCOPE OF RESEARCH

The stagnancy in the education sector has affected the students, teachers and parents in many ways. Some students have not been able to give their final exams and the remaining are uncertain if they will get a proper job post lockdown due to the sharp fall in the economies of many countries. The future looks uncertain and hazy. Teachers have been not able to complete the assessment procedure and also they are facing challenge of sudden transition i.e change from the traditional means of teaching to virtual teaching. Hence proper study is required to focus onto the problems faced by

students as well as teachers to overcome the effect of the pandemic in the education sector and suggest suitable measures.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To understand the impact of COVID-19 on the Education Sector
- To study the attitude of students and teachers towards Digital Learning
- To find out the Digital Learning tools used by teachers and students

Research Methodology:

For the purpose of the present study, both primary and secondary data has been used.

• Primary Data-

Primary data is collected from 30 college teachers and 50 College students across Thane District. On line survey method was used to collect data from respondents. Questionnaire was prepared in the form of Google Form and circulated over an email and through other informal mode viz WhatsApp, Telegram etc. Data is presented by using tables and pie charts. For the purpose of analysis of data, the simplest statistical tools were employed.

Secondary sources:

The secondary data has been obtained from the following sources:

- E- Magazines & E-Journals
- E-Newspapers
- Internet websites

1.4 Data Analysis and Interpretation:

The respondents were categorized into two groups for analysis - Students and Teachers across Thane District. The students were within the age group of 16-24 having mean age of 20 years. The respondents were chosen from various stream viz, Commerce, Arts, Science and professional category.

Demographic structure of the respondents:

	College Teachers
Male	11
Female	19
Total	30

Qualification of Professor	Number of Respondents
Post Graduate	18
M.Phil /P.hd	07
Professional Degree	05
Total	30

	College Students
Higher Secondary	15
Undergraduate	25
Post graduate	10
Total	50

Analysis of Data collected from Teacher:

Platform used by teachers for delivering lectures

As shown in the above chart, most of the respondents use Zoom (43%) and Google classroom (38%) platform for delivering online lectures followed by Microsoft teams (29%). Very few respondents (5%) use you tube videos and about 3% of the respondents use other platforms like skype, Cisco Webex, Go To meeting etc.

Problems in delivering Online Lectures:

Most of the teacher respondents (54%) complained of facing technical issue while conducting online lectures. Technical issued faced by them were “unable to share screen at times or proper use of teaching pedagogies, login issues, connectivity problems etc”. About 34% of the respondents had complained of lack of adequate infrastructure for conducting online lecture whereas 29% of the respondents do not have sufficient private space for delivering lecture in peaceful manner. Also few respondents (6%) accepted that they do not have enough digital learning tools like powerpoint presentation, videos, e-resources etc. to conduct online lectures.

Analysis of data collected from Students:

Most of the respondents (68%) agreed that they enjoyed attending online lectures without any glitches. Around 24% of the student respondents admitted that they face difficulty and at times are unable to understand or connect with the lecture. Whereas about 8% of the respondents admitted that sometimes it becomes little difficult to understand and get the doubts clear.

Do you face any issue while attending online lectures?

Around 32% of the respondents did not face any issue while attending online lectures whereas 22% sometimes face connectivity issue while attending online lecture. About 46% of the respondents revealed that they face difficulty in attending lectures due to connectivity issue, security issue, lack of learning environment at home and sharing the same device amongst siblings.

Do you think online learning is a concept that can be incorporated into the education system post covid period too?

There is a major positive response from the respondents (43%) regarding incorporating digital learning in the education system post covid period whereas the other respondents give a doubt owing to the issues faced by them.

1.5 Findings:

The pandemic has projected the importance of technology, leading to a greater degree of acceptance of the Learning Apps as a medium of learning. Students and teachers are growing increasingly comfortable with digital learning. This also provides a greater scope for Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality to try their applicability as an aid to education.

Every teacher is trying hard to develop skills required to handle the students in an online setup and teach with ease. E-learning resources are developed to create better understanding. The students are also cooperating and utilizing the technology in the best possible manner to their advantage.

Like there are two sides to a coin, the advantages of online platforms and e-learning come with certain disadvantages. In most households, children do not have a separate device like a laptop or a computer for educational purposes. They will have to borrow their parent's device in order to access the online lectures on various e-learning platforms. This is very inconvenient in the case of working parents since work from home has become a necessity during the time of this lockdown.

Every child has a different pace of studying and grasping information. A large number of students find it very difficult to cope up with what the teacher is teaching in these online lectures and hence they lag behind.

1.6 Suggestion for construction of strong base for Digital learning:

There should be restructuring in the way learning is distributed; pedagogies should evolve as per the requirements of online classes, and teachers should be given additional training to help them implement the new processes correctly and teach more effectively.

Advanced tools that would help create a replica of a physical classroom and keep the peer-to-peer learning should be further developed.

Virtual Reality, and Mixed Reality should be leveraged on to build these virtual classrooms and create better visualization of concepts.

To make Digital Learning mainstream, it is essential to patch the deep Digital Divide that runs through the nation, and make good and cost effective Network services available nationwide.

1.7 Conclusion:

Online learning/ Digital Learning came as a light at the end of the tunnel. During these tough times e-learning was the only ray of hope. The shift to Digital Learning puts greater emphasis on the need for better and updated study materials using technologies like QR Codes, VR etc. A look into the security concerns with online video conferencing and devising a way to fix them would be very helpful.

Thus, when the dust settles, the Education System must conserve and incorporate the efficacy of Digital Learning to Classroom Teaching to improve pedagogical effectiveness. This lockdown is also a prediction of the future, where most jobs could be done with the help of technology. One must make oneself aware of the new changes and must take steps accordingly. Thus, there is a great growth in Online Courses, encouraging students and professionals to enhance their skills while at home.

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